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Fig.3 The interface of C/Al composite by TEM

Fig.4 The SIMS Spectrogram of C/Al composite.

APPLICATION OF C/Cu COMPOSITE MATERIAL ON BRUSHES

Wu Yuing, Zhang Guoding
(Institute of Composite Material, Shanghai Jiao Tong
University, Shanghai, China)

ABSTRACT

To improve the performance of brushes has become a key subject with the development in new types electric machines. We made works in this yield. This paper introduce the C/Cu composite material brush.

We utilizing the excellent conductivity and high temperature resistant, small in diameter, light in weight and performance designability of composite material produce C/Cu composite brush.

Comparing composite brush with usual brush after more than 1200 hours dynamical running experiment in a 55kW d.c. machine, shows that the current density is increased by 5 times ($36\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$), the width of no-spark commutating region is increased by 5-10 times, the no load loss is decreased by 15-25%. For adapt various demands from different kinds of electric machine we can get different purpose of brushes by varying the proportion and structure of C/Cu composite brush.

C/Cu composite brush resolves a key problem for electric machine reform recent.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years development in military and industrial technology requires to produce electric machines with great rate and larger power, but smaller in size and lighter in weight, and for direct current machines, better commutating characteristic. It is obvious that appeared commercial brushes can't satisfy the above mentioned demands.

Current density of commercial electro-graphite brush is smaller than $12\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$, (C-Cu brush is $15\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$) so number of brushes is increased with increased machine power rating. Thus the size of the commutating equipment is increased. This makes electric machine more complex in structure, large in size and heavier in weight. Moreover the uneven current density between brushes connected in parallel in a electric machine will cause serious commutating spark under overload transient period. The commutating spark of military machines will expose its location.

Many facts have shown that improvement of brush's performance and structure is one of the key problems for electric machine. So it is necessary to develop new brushes with higher current density and great rate and better commutating characteristic slipping contact performance.

In recent twenty years scientists and specialists of various countries have carried out a great deal research works. They pay attention to the improvement of brush materials, brush structure, manufacturing method, working environment, working state etc. For instance, using powder metallurgy or liquid-state metal soaking method, metals such as

copper and silver with good electric conductivity and graphite are composed to form metal-graphite brushes.

These newly designed brushes markedly increases its own current density and decreases its contacts e.m.f. drop. Others produce brushes with metallic wire and carbon fibers. Another newly designs brushes are liquid-metal brush and brushes with mosaic metallic (Cu or Ag) columns. As carbon fibers is a good conductor and wear-resistant and also scorch-resistant to electric, etc, it has been used to make composite brushes.

The U.S. scientists have produced C/Cu composite brush, which is used in large single pole electric machines. Its current density is 500A/cm² and commutating peripheral speed is 200m/s. In England C/Cu composite brushes are used in 7000 HP icebreakers.

In short, the above mentioned research work have made a great progress in raising brush current density, but the commutating and wear-resistant problems are still retained, and it is necessary to be solved.

In this paper a new kind of C/Cu composite graphite brush will be introduced. It features high current density, good commutation ability, wear-resistant and higher peripheral speed.

EXPERIMENTAL

In order to adapt various demands for different kind of electric machines, we have produced a new kind of brush i.e. C/Cu composite graphite brush utilizing the performance designability of composite material. The C/Cu composite brush is made of C/Cu composite material and graphite, they mix with each other and form an uneven structure. It features high current carrying capability excellent commutating performance and wear-resistant. The good features of graphite brush i.e. high conductivity and wear-resistant are still retained in the C/Cu composite brush. Utilizing the composite material's low contact e.m.f. drop, good conductivity and composite proportion variability, thus the current carrying capability and commutating performance of brush have been greatly improved.

Fig.1 Commutating performance of usual brush and composite brush

- + D 172 7.2 A/cm²
- o 6# C/Cu composite 18 A/cm²
- * 14# C/Cu composite 36 A/cm²

rying capability and commutating performance of brush have been greatly improved.

We have carried out a systematic study on selection of graphite basis

material and selection of carbon fibre, C/Cu composite technology brush structure and former process technology. This yields a scientific bases for design of C/Cu composite material brush. After more than ten times (more than 1000 hours) dynamical running experiment in a 55 kW d.c. machine, it turns out that the newly designed brushes possess the expected performance i.e. high current carrying capability, excellent commutation, low power loss, wear-resistant etc.

1. High Current Density

The needs 20 graphite brushes used in a 2-pole 55 kW machine. Current density of brush is 7.2 A/cm². Instead, there required only 4-8 C/Cu composite brushes in the same machine. The current density of the C/Cu composite brush is 18-36 A/cm². So the number of brush is decreased by 60-80% when using C/Cu composite brush. Besides, although the current density is increased by 2.5-5 times. (see Table 1), the commutating performance is greatly improved (see Fig.1). Decreasing number of brushes means decreasing size of commutating equipment and copper saving and this in turn simplifies the structure of machine and reduces machine size and weight. In large current machines, the C/Cu composite brush can decrease unsafe factor which is unavoidable due to uneven distribution of brush current in a great number of brushes parallely connected.

Table 1 Current density of D-172 brush and C/Cu composite brush*

	number of brush	current density of a brush A/cm ²	commutating performance
electro-graphite brush	20	7.2	poorer
C/Cu composite material	4 - 8	18 - 36	good

*) Electric machine character N=55kW n=2500route/min V=26.2m/min I=288A

2. Excellent Commutating Performance

In our experiment the commutating performance is investigated by the resonance method, by this method we obtain the commutating spark limit relative to the interpole current strength. The commutating performance of brushes is expressed by the width of no spark commutating region. The broader the region, the better the commutation effect. Fig.1 shows the commutating effect of 5 different C/Cu composite brushes compared with D172 graphite brush. They all were mounted on the same machine. Form curves in Fig.1 it is obvious that the no spark commutating region of any one of C/Cu brushes is broader than that of D172 graphite brush, even though current-carrying density of the former is 2.5-5 times of the later. At full-load, the width of no spark commutating region is still increased by five to ten times. These indicate that the C/Cu composite material brush can endure large overload current density.

3. Lower No Load Loss

No load loss of a electric machine means mechanical loss. Certainly the frictional loss caused by the brush slipping along the commutator is also included. So the measured mechanical loss of a machine under the same runing condition except with different kind of brushes will show the difference of the commutator frictional loss. Table 2 shows no load loss of a machine using C/Cu composite or graphite brushes. It is seen that different C/Cu composite materials have different no-load loss. But they all are less than that of D172 brush. Usually no load loss of the former is less than the later by 12-25%.

Table 2. No Load Loss

brush types	number of brush	no load loss	electric density A/cm ²
D-172	20	2264 W	7.2
D-172	4	1920 W	7.2
14#C/Cu composite	4	1910 W	36
5#C/Cu composite	8	1880 W	18
8#C/Cu composite	8	1710 W	18

4. Wear Resistance

Wear resistance is also an important index to brush slipping performance. Table 3 is a comparative result of D172 and C/Cu composite brush. It can be seen that C/Cu composite brush features better wear-resistance than D172 brush.

Table 3 Wear Resistance of Brush

brush types	wear value	electric density A/cm ²	running time h
D-172	0.23	7.2	50
8#C/Cu composite	0.13	7.2	50

5. Performance Designability

As C/Cu composite brush is made by C/Cu composite material with graphite basis they are mixed in an uneven state. So we can get different brushes of different purpose by varying the proportion of C/Cu composite and graphite material using different types of carbon fiber, different ways of compounding and different treatment. Thus we can obtain brushes with different current ductivity, different electric resistance along different brush direction and different mechanical performance.

Fig.2 and Table 2,3 have expressed the commutating and mechanical performance of various types of C/Cu composite brush. One can chose the types of C/Cu composite brush according to his own demand.

Fig.2 Commutating cure of various types of C/Cu composite brush.

2# C/Cu composite	21.6A/cm ²
3# C/Cu composite	18 A/cm ²
4# C/Cu composite	18 A/cm ²
12#C/Cu composite	18 A/cm ²
9# C/Cu composite	36 A/cm ²
8# C/Cu composite	18 A/cm ²

Brushes made from C/Cu composite material with graphite basis is uneven in structure. It features high current carrying capability, excellent commutating behavior, good slip contact performance, low power loss and because of its light weight, lower price and with excellent performance designability. It is expected that it will become a new kind of widely

used brushes and will be as a nice gift dedicated to the electric machine reform.

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